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VOLUME 1

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“MY HEART SCREAMS OF THANKSGIVING”

My heart screams of thanksgiving
Words of the mouth can't even compare
For I am so happy, there's no denying
This is a family I truly care.

Out of nowhere, I came
Popped out like a flash of lightning
This family received me like a queen
With heart up, arms outstretched, and teaching with care.

So, my heart screams out of thanksgiving
Once a seedling now grown
Once a newbie now flourishing
Thank you for I was sown.

Now my journey continues on
Though the chapters written I wish to extend
But the Author of life beckon
A different design, Another plan He sends.

My book is still unfinished
But memories gained forever be cherished
I may be gone for now, surely, I'll be back
So please... wish me all your good luck.

Like an eagle, I will soar high
Not to fail you my school and my family in Baybay
My triumph is yours, not to deny
So, with your dreams, wishes, and prayers I fly.

My heart screams of thanksgiving
Thanks to my new station, KIS for welcoming
Today this is the book I am writing
Tomorrow let's all sit down find ourselves reading.

